

EXAMPLE OF COPING STRATEGIES IN ADOLESCENTS TO BE

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Abstract: This article provides information about coping strategies, information about the manifestation of coping strategies in adolescents.

Key words: adolescent, intuition, coping strategies, crisis period, "transition period", conflict, stress, behavior,

Adolescence is a period of transition from childhood to adulthood, characterized by its physical and psychological characteristics. At this stage, the physical and psychological development of children is greatly accelerated, their interest in various things in life increases, the desire for novelty increases, their character is formed, the spiritual world becomes richer, conflicts predominate. Adolescence is a period of puberty, characterized by the emergence of new sensations, sensations and even complex issues with an education of sexual life at this age begin to undergo drastic changes in the development of a teenager. These changes are both physiological and psychological changes. Teenagers try to keep themselves as adults.

They strive to show their dignity, abilities and capabilities to a certain extent to their comrades and teachers. This condition can be easily seen even by simple observation. For this reason, adolescence is characterized by such psychological manifestations as "transition period", "crisis period", "difficult period". This period is also distinguished by its richness to the conflict for adolescents. And the way adolescents get out of these conflicting, circulatory, and stressful situations depends on how many strategies they choose. Someone recognizes coping strategies that are decisive for circulation in this process, someone else chooses coping strategies that avoid or circumvent circulation. And a thorough study of these processes will help us to avoid situations with circulatory stress, which in the future can occur with adolescents.

The problem of coping behavior has always been one of the most pressing problems facing humanity. After all, the social development of a person in all respects, his activity and self-development in the quality of a person depend largely on this process. If the members of the society have enough information about their psychological possibilities, achievements and shortcomings of a certain circle, this will allow them to easily overcome the various difficulties that they face in life, to make more productive use of their opportunities, to form a deeper, positive and peculiar picture about themselves.

The concept of "coping strategy" is also widely analyzed as process resource

management. According to assumptions, the elimination of life's complications is essentially through the mobilization of personal resources is done.

Coping strategy and its methods are distinguished from defense mechanisms by constructive active necessity is held and is an attempt to avoid unpleasantness through the situation. The subject of coping in psychology exists, and it is a special research area of emotional mechanism and rational regulation in a person learning life situations in accordance with his goals according to his goal optimal behavior will carry out reconstruction.

Coping behavior of a person in stressful situations is a response reaction in stressful situations is important for Especially in the period of adolescence, it is necessary to take a serious look at this process. That's it taking into account the relationship between coping behavior and stress response in adolescents empirical study of social psychological factors related to and conditionally accepted it was planned to analyze its results based on the criteria. To accomplish this task research methods were chosen.

It should also be noted that sometimes every teenager adequately assesses his capabilities in stressful situations. May be somewhat difficult to obtain. In our opinion, such a challenge is stressful it can be explained by the fact that he does not have enough idea about the situations.

Coping strategies are called coping strategies in foreign literature (ing. Coping, coping strategy) - this is help people to overcome stress and problematic situation (eng. COPE with) will give. The concept includes cognitive, emotional, and behavioral strategies used to cope with stress and in general, it combines psychologically difficult situations of everyday life. This concept is Russia. It is a widely used and deeply developed concept in the psychological school.

Coping strategies are a broad concept with a long and complicated history (Compas et al. Difficult life occupying a person with situations (coping-behavior, from English. "to cope" - to cope, to cope with something). Coping strategies in foreign and domestic psychology in the 50-60s of the 20th century began to be studied in The concept of coping was first coined by R. Lazarus and S. Folkman included in the framework of the transactional model of stress. According to this model, stress and emotions are environmental processes and the result of human interaction. Copying is "extrinsic and intrinsic to the human being constantly changing ways of knowledge and behavior to overcome the demands" (Lazarus, Folkman, 1984, p. 141). Nowadays, coping usually refers to voluntary and conscious actions(Lazarus, 2006; Folkman et al.. 1979)¹ although some researchers in youth psychology are more extensive has a definition. Second,

coping involves all forms of emotion regulation, including non-compulsory, related to differences in temperament and habitual behavior (Compas, 1998) there are processes. In general, coping is a variable process.

More recently, researchers dealing with coping strategies are more resourceful than coping began to follow the approach. "Allocation of resources" in a resource-based approach. It is emphasized that there is a process (commodity of resources), which some people despite different living conditions explains how they manage to be healthy and fit (Frydenberg, Lewis, 2002) Albert Bandura

The self-efficacy construct developed by (Frydenberg, Lewis) can also be considered as an important source of influence on coping behavior (Frydenberg, Lewis)

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